

MICRO – MACRO PORE EVOLUTION OF A SANDSTONE UNDER SUPERCRITICAL-CO₂-AGING

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ABSTRACT

Carbon Capture and Storage (CCS) has become a topic of interest among the scientific community since Global Warming was first brought up. CCS is a widely spread technique proposed to reduce the concentration of CO₂ in the air, which, according to the Intergovernmental Panel for Climate Change (IPCC), is the greenhouse gas effect emitted in greater quantity [6]. CCS consists of sequestering carbon dioxide, either from the atmosphere or directly from its emission point, and injecting it to underground adequate rock formations. There are several types of geological CO₂ storage alternatives, among which the most studied ones are the storage in partially or totally depleted oil and gas reservoirs, deep saline aquifers and unminable coal beds [1].

When analyzing the feasibility of injecting CO₂ into a certain formation, it is necessary to evaluate a series of aspects. On the one hand, the variation of the properties of the reservoir rock chosen should be analyzed before and after the supercritical CO₂ (scCO₂) aging is performed. It is of vital relevance to determine the rock's properties in its pristine state, as these will determine the storing volume available [2]. Particularly, properties such as permeability, porosity and mineralogical composition, have a great influence in this matter. The modification in time of the rock's characteristics due to the interaction with scCO₂ will directly affect its storage capacity. On the other hand, it is also essential to analyze the storage's integrity, weighing in each case the seal loss bounding mechanisms involved [3].

The aim of the research developed and presented in this article is to study the interactions produced micro and macro structurally when scCO₂ is introduced to an oil and gas depleted reservoir rock. The reservoir rock studied is characterized for being a well-sorted glauconitic sandstone composed of marine sediments, present in the Salamanca Formation of the San Jorge Gulf Basin (Argentinian Patagonia). In order to be able to investigate the variation in the rock's properties due to scCO₂ injection, a series of tests were performed. Among them, the Uniaxial Compressive Test, Mercury Intrusion Porosimetry (MIP), Scanning Electronic Microscopy (SEM), Electronic Microscopy, X-Ray Diffraction (XRD) and X-Ray Fluorescence (XRF) were carried out. The mentioned tests were performed over two sets of specimens, the first one, composed of cores and fragments of pristine sandstone, and the second one collected a group of scCO₂ altered specimens. The aging process was executed by introducing the group of water-saturated-cores and pieces of sandstone into a CO₂ reaction cell, under 10.5 MPa and 60°C, during a 30-day-period. The pressure and temperature were chosen so as to guarantee the injected gas was on a supercritical state, keeping

the testing conditions as close to reality as possible. The developed procedure is similar to the ones presented by Rathnaweera et al. (2015) [5] and Gholami et al. (2022) [4].

Preliminary results obtained from Uniaxial Compressive Tests performed in both pristine and carbonated sandstone cores of variable length/diameter ratios are presented in Figure 1. As it might be observed, after 30-day-supercritical-CO₂ aging, the studied rock shows a reduction in its compressive strength. It might also be observed that the sandstone's behavior becomes more ductile. These results are similar to those reported by Rathnaweera et al. (2015) [5].

In terms of porosity, two main modifications were detected. Firstly, it can be mentioned that there has been a slight reduction in the sandstone's porosity after its exposure to carbon dioxide (carbonated specimens presented porosities 1.2% smaller than pristine specimens). Secondly, it can be noted that the size pore distribution varied (Figure 2), increasing the percentage of pores with a smaller diameter. From these two statements, it could be preliminarily considered that during the scCO₂-aging of the samples, chemical precipitation occurred in the bigger diameter pores. This hypothesis will be contrasted with the analysis of the SEM, XRD and XRF results.

Fig. 1. Stress-Strain curves for tested specimens.

Fig. 2. Pore diameter distribution for tested specimens.

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